

Hands-On Activity in 3rd Year Industrial Engineering and Management: Students' Perspective

Beatriz Silva¹, Inês Silva¹, Maria Pereira¹, Maria Inês Torres¹, Marta Ribeiro¹, Raquel Oliveira¹, Sandra Costa¹, Anabela Alves^{1,2}

¹ Department of Production and Systems, School of Engineering, University of Minho, Guimarães, Portugal

² ALGORITMI/LASI Research Center, School of Engineering, University of Minho, Guimarães, Portugal

Email: a104680@alunos.uminho.pt, a104681@alunos.uminho.pt, a104764@alunos.uminho.pt, a104768@alunos.uminho.pt, a104773@alunos.uminho.pt, a104694@alunos.uminho.pt, a104776@alunos.uminho.pt, anabela@dps.uminho.pt

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Abstract

This paper presents a hands-on classroom activity designed to simulate a production system using a baton-touch operating mode in the course of Production Systems Organization. The activity was carried out by a team of students of third-year Industrial Engineering and Management as part of an interactive learning experience aimed at understanding production processes and enhancing teamwork skills. In this simulation, students worked in teams to replicate the operations of a textile company (chosen by the team), focusing on identifying current situation, improving workflow and layout, resource allocation, and process management. The exercise was structured to challenge students to apply theoretical knowledge to a practical scenario and learn tools (e.g. Product-Quantity Analysis, SIPOC and Spaghetti diagram, balancing methods, Standard Work Sheets, Skills Competences), encouraging critical thinking and problem-solving skills. The teams had to define the demand and production rates, sustainable operations, and ensuring product quality throughout the process. Feedback from the activity highlighted its effectiveness in providing a practical understanding of textile production operations. Students reported a deeper appreciation for the complexity of production systems and the importance of communication and coordination among team members. The hands-on approach not only reinforced theoretical concepts but also emphasized the significance of adaptability and efficient problem solving in industrial environments. Overall, this activity provided valuable experiential learning, offering students a comprehensive insight into textile manufacturing while fostering teamwork, leadership, and operational efficiency.

Keywords: Active Learning; Industrial Engineering and Management Education; Project Based Learning.

1 Introduction

Active learning fundamentally differs from passive learning by positioning the student as the protagonist of their own educational process. While passive learning is characterized by the unidirectional reception of information, where the student assumes the role of a listener and content receiver, active learning involves dynamic participation, encouraging students to interact, question, and apply the knowledge acquired in practical contexts. This approach promotes a deeper and more meaningful understanding, facilitating retention and the ability to apply knowledge in real-world situations (Felder & Brent, 2006).

In recent years, active learning has expanded beyond traditional formats to include methodologies such as Design Thinking, gamification, and project-based learning, each aiming to increase student engagement and promote the development of higher-order thinking skills. Design Thinking, in particular, has shown to be effective in fostering creativity, empathy, and interdisciplinary collaboration among students (Alvarado, 2025). Similarly, the use of games and digital tools, commonly referred to as Game-Based Learning (GBL), has proven to enhance motivation, participation, and the ability to apply knowledge in dynamic scenarios, while also contributing to digital literacy (Rodríguez-Ferrer et al., 2023).

These active methodologies have also been linked to improved student well-being and preparation for professional challenges. By engaging students in real-life simulations and problem-solving tasks, active learning strategies cultivate key skills such as communication, teamwork, and decision-making. Furthermore,

research shows that active engagement in academic activities increases satisfaction and supports emotional, social, and academic well-being (Ribeiro-Silva et al., 2022). The implementation of such strategies, especially when integrated with technological resources, creates a flexible and interactive learning environment, reinforcing the pedagogical value of student-centered education.

In engineering education, active learning methodologies have gained increasing relevance for their capacity to foster engagement, critical thinking, and autonomy among students. Within this context, the Production Systems Organization (PSO) course integrates hands-on activities and Project-Based Learning (PBL), often in collaboration with real companies. These methods have proven particularly effective, placing students at the centre of the learning process and encouraging them to identify real-world problems and design practical, feasible solutions.

Within the scope of the Production Systems Organization course, the implementation of active learning methodologies, such as hands-on activities and Project-Based Learning in partnership with a company, has proven to be particularly effective. This methodology places students at the centre of the educational process, assigning them the responsibility of identifying real-world problems and developing practical solutions, fostering essential skills for the job market.

In PSO course, these methodologies have been used, emphasizing the importance of engaging students in projects that reflect real industrial challenges (Alves & Soares, 2020; Soares & Alves, 2019, 2021a, 2021b). The teacher of this course had been publishing the results of the feedback questionnaire fulfilled by the course students regarding this pedagogical experience. However, in these references were the results from the teachers' perspective. In this context, this paper discusses this pedagogical experience and its results from the students' perspective. The paper authors are, mainly, a student team that developed the assigned project aligned with this active approach, challenging the team to apply the concepts learned in a real industrial setting.

The motivation for this work stems from the team's participation in the PSO course project, which challenged students to reconfigure an existing production system using Lean principles. The team chose to work with a real company and focused on transforming a traditional production layout into manufacturing cells, adopting the baton-touch operating mode. This choice required the application of theoretical tools to real constraints and encouraged the development of decision-making, problem-solving, and technical skills in a practical context.

The main objectives of this paper are to describe the development of the hands-on activity from the student team's perspective, highlight the tools and methodologies applied throughout the project, and reflect on the skills acquired during this process. In addition, the paper aims to demonstrate the pedagogical value of engaging with real industrial environments and how active learning strategies can enhance both academic learning and professional preparedness.

This paper is organized in five sections. The first one is the introduction, where the objectives are presented. The second section outlines the study context. The third section presents the project development and hands-on activity preparation as well as the methodology adopted by the team, including company selection, analysis of the production system, the reconfiguration process, the lessons learned and hands-on simulation preparation. The fourth section presents the results and discussion, focusing on the simulation model, its implementation, and impact. Finally, the fifth section draws the main conclusions and highlights the competencies acquired and the pedagogical value of this hands-on learning experience.

2 Study Context

Production Systems Organization is a curricular unit offered in the 3rd year, 1st semester of the Industrial Engineering and Management degree at the University of Minho. This curricular unit aims to provide students with the necessary knowledge and tools to analyse, design, and improve production systems, focusing on efficiency, sustainability, and innovation. Through theoretical foundations and practical applications, PSO enables students to develop a comprehensive understanding of production management and process improvement.

The course assessment methodology combines theoretical quizzes to evaluate students' knowledge and understanding of key concepts, as well as a company-based project that allows them to apply these concepts in a real-world setting. The proposed work was to be developed by teams of seven to eight members, promoting collaboration and knowledge exchange among participants. This involved conducting a detailed diagnosis of a company's production system, considering production factors, transformation processes, and products (goods and/or services).

To achieve this, an initial research phase was carried out using indexed databases such as Scopus and Web of Science to provide a theoretical foundation for the analysis and proposed solutions. This was the first of three milestones for this project, completed in week 6 of the course. During this phase, teams had to prepare two A3 reports, summarizing scientific articles on the design and reconfiguration of production systems, such as assembly lines, cells, and job shops. More about this activity could be seen in Alves, 2020.

Subsequently, students' teams were required to choose between creating a fictitious company or working with an existing one to collect data and analyse its current situation. They were tasked with providing a critical assessment of its operations to identify waste, problems, and their underlying causes. Week 10 marked the completion of the second milestone, which involved an intermediate presentation of their findings, also following the format of a 5-minute presentation and a 5-minute discussion.

Finally, the third milestone, taking place in the 16th and final week, was the culmination of the project, in which teams proposed improvement strategies for the company or sector, supported by a cost-benefit analysis. The application of the 10R principles (Rethink, Reduce, Reuse, Repair, Refurbish, Remanufacture, Repurpose, Recycle, Recover, and Refuse) (Kirchherr & Piscicelli, 2019; Potting et al., 2017) was also emphasized to ensure a positive impact on the sustainability of the production system. In addition to theoretical and diagnostic analysis, teams were also responsible for simulating the proposed production system, either by producing a prototype of the chosen product or through an alternative representation that demonstrated the implemented improvements. This final presentation lasted 30 minutes, followed by a 10-minute discussion. Table 1 presents the criteria and weight for the deliverable of this milestone.

Table 1. Assessment criteria and weight of each for deliverable of milestone 3.

Criteria	Weight
Preparation and creativity	15%
Content exploration	15%
Presentation and delivery	25%
Demonstration and simulation	25%
Results and discussion	15%
Submission of all materials on time	5%

This challenging project not only provided a valuable practical experience but also brought tangible benefits to the analysed company, reinforcing the importance of applying PSO concepts to solve real-world industrial problems. A summary of the weight of each assessment component for the course, including the project and

the quizzes, is presented in Table 2, which outlines how each element contributes to the final grade of the course.

Table 2. Weight of assessment components.

Assessment components	Weight
3 Individual Quizzes	30% (10% each)
Project (Milestone 1 + Milestone 2 + Milestone 3)	70% (25% + 15% + 30%)

3 Project development and hands-on simulation activity preparation

To achieve this project, a team was formed consisting of seven female students (the authors of this paper) and one male student, who was a working student and not enrolled on a full-time basis. All team members had previously collaborated in other courses and academic years, which facilitated group dynamics and project coordination.

At the outset of the project, the team decided to collaborate with a real company rather than construct a hypothetical case. The primary motivation was to gain a more practical and applied understanding of industrial processes, rather than relying solely on theoretical assumptions. By engaging with an existing company, the team aimed to immerse in a tangible manufacturing environment, confronting real-world constraints and operational challenges. This approach allowed the team to observe first-hand the intricacies of production workflows, resource management, and decision-making processes, providing a depth of learning that a fictional scenario could not offer.

3.1 Company selection, contact and visits

To identify a suitable enterprise for the study, the team conducted extensive research on companies operating in the vicinity of the university. While many of the potential candidates were textile manufacturers - given the predominance of this industry in the region - the team also explored alternatives in different sectors. The considered enterprises specialized in footwear production, prefabricated housing, and other manufacturing domains. The team goal was to find a company that would be both accessible and open to collaboration. After narrowing down the options, the team reached out to several enterprises, initiating communication to assess their willingness to participate in our project.

Establishing contact with enterprises proved to be a challenging process, as obtaining responses required persistent effort. The team initiated multiple outreach attempts, and after considerable effort, the team successfully established a connection with one enterprise due to a group member's acquaintance within the company. Coincidentally, around the same time, the team also received a positive response from another enterprise. Given this unexpected opportunity, the team decided to divide and conduct visits to both companies. These visits were crucial in refining understanding of the production environment and collecting relevant data.

Prior to the visits, the team meticulously prepared a list of key questions to ensure that the team gathered comprehensive information on manufacturing processes, equipment usage, and workflow dynamics. By engaging with employees and supervisors on-site, the team gained valuable insights into the daily operations and challenges faced by each enterprise. After careful consideration, the team chose to proceed with the company that demonstrated the greatest openness to collaboration and willingness to share relevant information. The team expressed our gratitude to the other company for their time and support, acknowledging the valuable insights gained from the visit.

Following our initial visit, the team continued engaged with the selected company by maintaining open communication via email. As the research progressed, new questions and areas of interest emerged, prompting to reach out for further clarifications. The company was receptive to inquiries, providing additional insights that enriched the understanding of the production process. Recognizing the importance of first-hand observation, the team arranged a second site visit with the entire group.

During this visit (Figure 1), the team focused on mapping the factory floor layout and resolving outstanding queries. The team had the opportunity to interact with an engineer overseeing the production section, who provided a more detailed explanation of the workflow. This deeper engagement allowed the observation of the machines in operation, enhancing the comprehension of the production dynamics and reinforcing the relevance of the study.

Figure 1. Visit to the company.

3.2 Selection and critical analysis of the study sector

Given the large dimensions of the selected company, the team decided to focus on the reconfiguration of the dyeing sector, as it would be unfeasible to analyse the entire factory within the limited project time frame, which was three months. This decision was supported by the fact that the engineer responsible for the guided tour mentioned that this sector presented the highest waste, both in terms of time and in terms of other operational aspects.

Therefore, to understand the current conditions of the company and identify potential issues, the team carried out various analyses, which the team learn in class and applied to the real context. Thus, the team started by classifying the production system according to quantity, layout, demand satisfaction mode, nature of products, and nature of material flow (Alves, 2016).

To better understand the production process, the team conducted a product-quantity (P-Q) analysis, as the company manufactures various types of sheets, resulting in the production of different types of rolls. However, due to the project's time limitations, the team chose to focus only on the rolls corresponding to the most demanded products, which were cotton rolls followed by linen rolls.

Next, the team developed a SIPOC diagram for the dyeing section to identify the suppliers, inputs, processes, outputs, and customers of this specific unit (George et al., 2005). This was followed by a mapping of the workflow for the products under analysis, which allowed us to understand the sequence of machines each roll passed through within the section, providing a clear view of the production sequence. At this stage, it was crucial to analyse all activities for each product, distinguishing between value-added (VA) and non-value-added (NVA) activities. To gain a clearer view of the entire process, the team developed the current layout of the section using AutoCAD, accurately representing all machines, corridors, and storage areas to a 1:1000 scale.

Additionally, the team traced the path of the rolls in the current layout and calculated the distances travelled by each of them. To better understand the company's situation, the team analysed performance measures such

as takt time, cycle time, work in process, among others, which allowed us to quantify critical operational aspects and identify possible improvements.

3.3 Production system reconfiguration phase

After analysing and understanding the company's initial conditions, it was possible to proceed to the system reconfiguration phase. During this process, the team identified that the system in place at the company was functional, also known as a workshop system, and proceeded to transform it into an operational cell with the Baton-Touch operating mode. The Baton-Touch mode was employed, where each participant was responsible for a specific task in the production chain, passing on the responsibility to the next team member, mimicking a real-world production line (Baudin, 2003).

At this stage, the team defined a set of balancing objectives, such as to reduce the number of workstations and cycle time (increasing production rate), increasing efficiency while considering operational and production constraints, increasing profits (difference between revenue and costs), and reducing costs. To achieve these objectives, the team applied the Wild method for balancing by grouping products with similar production steps, using aggregated load to then organize them efficiently into workstations, ensuring an improved production flow and waste reduction (Alves, 2024).

Next, the team created a relationship diagram, focused not on the relationship between sections, but rather between machines, which led us to develop two layout proposals (Figure 2). After the new design, the team once again used AutoCAD to calculate the distances travelled by each roll, which resulted in two solutions where the distances for linen rolls increased, which was considered normal, as the focus was more on the cotton roll path due to its higher demand.

Figure 2. Layout proposals to reduce distances (in Portuguese).

In both solutions, the team managed to reduce more than half of the distance travelled by the cotton rolls. In the end, the team chose the layout that, although it had a higher total distance travelled by both rolls, offered the shortest distance for the cotton roll. With the new layout, the team achieved a total reduction of about 95.6 meters in the distance travelled for the production of one cotton roll and one linen roll.

The proposal to implement a new production layout aims to reorganize the workflow in a more continuous and efficient way. Among the main advantages are the creation of a more organized production flow, the elimination of unnecessary activities, and the better use of available human potential. These factors contribute significantly to the increase in the company's productive efficiency, resulting, in the medium and long term, in lower operational costs.

However, the proposal also presents disadvantages that must be carefully considered. The movement and reorganization of machines, along with the necessary reconfiguration of the physical layout, involve a high initial cost. Additionally, it will be essential to provide training for operators, which represents another investment, the cost of training workers. These factors may have a financial impact in the short term, although significant operational benefits are expected in the future.

3.4 Lessons learned: theoretical vs real setting

Throughout the development and design of the layouts, the team applied the theoretical concepts acquired during the lessons in the course. However, the team quickly realized that it was not enough to strictly follow the methods. The company's reality presented a series of limitations and challenges that needed to be considered. Among the main constraints were physical limitations of the facilities, such as the available space and machine layout, as well as economic issues related to costs and the feasibility of the proposed changes. Additionally, operational factors, such as machine production capacity and material flow dynamics, also influenced the layout solutions. The practical experience within the company was essential, as it allowed us to understand how industrial engineering managers deal with these constraints on a daily basis, adjusting theoretical concepts to the complexity and specifics of the production environment.

3.5 Hands-on simulation preparation

The next phase of the project focused on translating the observations into a functional and physical simulation model. This stage required creativity, teamwork, and a high degree of responsibility, as the team aimed to construct a model that effectively demonstrated the production process in a simplified yet accurate manner.

The team selected key machines representative of the manufacturing process, including a gas-fired machine, a washing machine using caustic soda, a drying and ironing machine, and a foulard. To construct the simulation, the team utilized materials such as recycled cardboard boxes, kitchen paper rolls, scissors, paints, hot glue, markers, adhesive tape, and brushes. These materials enabled the creation of a tangible representation of the production sequence, allowing to analyse workflow efficiency and potential areas for improvement.

The project involved several trials and adjustments, as the team worked collectively to refine the accuracy and clarity of the model. In total, ten different simulation attempts were carried out to achieve the most accurate possible representation of the operating mode, ensuring that the baton-touch workflow was effectively conveyed. Furthermore, the team conducted multiple rehearsals to ensure that the presentation accurately reflected the real-world dynamics observed in the factory. This experience was both challenging and rewarding, as it allowed us to transform industrial complexity into a comprehensible visual format, reinforcing our understanding of the production environment and strengthening our ability to work collaboratively under pressure. In the hands-on simulation, the team specifically examined production processes for two types of textile products. By incorporating real-world parameters observed during the site visits, the team aimed to replicate the conditions and constraints encountered in the industry. The hands-on experience of developing and refining the simulation model reinforced the understanding of industrial operations, bridging the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application.

4 Results and discussion

The hands-on simulation played a key role in consolidating the team's understanding of the reconfigured production system and communicating it effectively to an academic audience. Developing the model required not only technical precision but also a high degree of adaptability, as the team aimed to balance simplification with realism. Over the course of the preparation, ten different configurations were tested and refined to ensure the most accurate and pedagogically effective representation of the manufacturing process using the baton-touch mode.

This iterative effort promoted collaborative problem-solving and highlighted the importance of teamwork in addressing practical challenges. By translating industrial complexity into a clear and engaging visual format, the team created a model that supported both learning and dissemination. Furthermore, the commitment to

active learning was evident throughout, from the decision to collaborate with a real company to the design and execution of the simulation.

As one team member highlighted:

"It is important to highlight that this project allowed me to truly experience the value of active learning, as it challenged me to take initiative, work collaboratively, and apply theoretical knowledge to real industrial problems, thereby strengthening my technical skills and preparing me for future professional challenges."

The entire process contributed significantly to the development of transversal competencies such as critical thinking, communication, and adaptability - skills that are essential for future professional practice in industrial engineering. For the presentation of this project, the team developed a scaled-down simulation, which was presented to the class. In this simulation, cardboard boxes were used to represent the various machines in the factory, such as the gassing machine, fabric washing and drying machines, among others. Additionally, kitchen paper rolls were used to simulate the fabric rolls (Figure 3).

Figure 3. The simulation of the process using practical and accessible materials and tools to represent the real process (in Portuguese).

Based on this sketch, the boxes were cut and labelled with the names of the respective machines, thus facilitating the understanding of the simulation by the observers. The boxes (representing the machines) were arranged on tables in the classroom, and each team member was assigned responsibility for one or two specific processes. During the simulation, the team members manually unrolled and rolled the paper rolls, simulating their passage through the corresponding machines.

To further support the classmates' understanding, everyday household items were used, such as a hairdryer (to simulate fabric drying) and an iron (to simulate the ironing process). Although these props do not accurately replicate the industrial procedures, the team believed they would help to clarify the process more clearly.

While the team was generally satisfied with the outcome of the simulation, it is important to note that not everything went as expected, particularly when compared to previous rehearsals. As this was a live presentation, it was essential that the narration of the processes - carried out by one team member - was synchronised with the actions performed by the others. However, factors such as potential nervousness, the inclusion of micro-processes (e.g., machine programming), or unforeseen issues (e.g., the fabric rolls getting stuck or being difficult to roll) occasionally led to a mismatch between the narration and the demonstration, requiring adjustments to the pacing.

Despite these challenges, the team believes that the simulation successfully achieved its main objective: to effectively convey the concept of a factory floor and the sequence of processes involved.

As one team member reflected:

"More than the presentation itself, the real challenge lay in the ability to accurately and clearly translate the dynamics of a factory environment, particularly regarding the implementation of the baton-touch mode."

One additional challenge was the arrangement of the machines. In order to ensure visibility for the entire class, it was not possible to replicate the exact layout used in the factory (as seen in Baton Touch). Instead, a layout was adopted that prioritised clarity and visibility for the audience. Figure 4 presents some photos taken during the classroom presentation conducted by the team.

Figure 4. Classroom presentation.

5 Conclusion

This paper presents a team perspective of a hands-on activity simulated in the classroom to represent the reconfiguration and improvement of a company's production system. Developed within the scope of the Production Systems Organization course, this project offered students the opportunity to apply theoretical concepts in a real industrial context, specifically focusing on the dyeing section of a textile company selected for its operational relevance and complexity.

Throughout the project, students applied a range of production analysis tools - such as P-Q analysis, SIPOC diagrams, spaghetti and layout mapping, value-added and non-value-added analysis, and balancing techniques. These tools enabled a systematic diagnosis of the current state and supported the design of a reconfigured system aligned with Lean Thinking principles (Womack & Jones, 1996). The transformation from a functional layout to a cellular production system, using the Baton-Touch operating mode, resulted in significant performance improvements, most notably a reduction of approximately 96 meters in the overall material flow for the company's most critical product line.

The autonomy granted to the team in selecting both the type of product and the partner company stimulated proactivity, responsibility, and strategic decision-making. This flexibility provided a deeper understanding of the challenges and dynamics of the industrial environment that the team is likely to face in the near future. By engaging with real-world situations, students were exposed to contexts that required adaptability, critical thinking, and the capacity to solve complex problems - competencies that are highly valued in today's job market. Moreover, contacting and collaborating with real companies enabled the development of essential soft skills, including communication, negotiation, and project management, all of which contribute directly to future professional readiness.

The pedagogical value of this experience lies in its ability to bridge the gap between theoretical instruction and practical application. By interacting directly with an industrial partner, conducting on-site visits, and navigating real operational constraints - such as space limitations, resource availability, and workflow complexity - students gained a deeper, more authentic understanding of industrial dynamics. The project demanded not only technical proficiency but also flexibility, creativity, and perseverance in problem-solving.

Furthermore, the development and presentation of a physical simulation model using accessible materials contributed to experiential learning and peer education. It facilitated the visualization of production processes

and helped communicate proposed improvements to an academic audience. Although minor challenges arose during the live demonstration, such as synchronizing actions and adapting layout visibility for the classroom setting, the simulation successfully conveyed the essence of the redesigned system.

In conclusion, this project demonstrated the effectiveness of integrating real-world challenges and active learning methodologies into engineering education. It provided a holistic learning experience that complemented theoretical knowledge with practical insight, preparing students more effectively for the complexity and multidimensionality of modern production systems.

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